

Human Resources Professionals' Perceptions of Quality of Working Life and Its Determinants: A Qualitative Study

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Abstract

Quality of working life is a multidimensional concept that refers to the level of physical, psychological, and social well-being of employees in the work environment. Human resources professionals hold a unique position in terms of quality of working life, as they are a professional group that both manages employee experience and is at the center of organizational processes. Therefore, examining the perceptions of human resources professionals the quality of working life constitutes an important research area for understanding organizational working conditions. The aim of this research is to reveal the perceptions of human resources professionals the quality of working life and the organizational factors that shape this perception. The research was conducted using a qualitative research method, and semi-structured interviews were conducted with 14 participants working in managerial positions in the human resources departments of companies operating in different sectors in Istanbul. Participants were reached using the snowball sampling method. The obtained data were analyzed using the MAXQDA 2020 program in accordance with the thematic analysis approach developed by Braun and Clarke (2006). The analysis identified six key themes influencing quality of working life: legal security and perception of employment, work structure and work-life balance, career management and fairness, organizational climate and participation, nature of work and qualification fit, and wage policy and economic satisfaction. The findings indicate that perceived job security, open communication, and job-person fit positively impact quality of working life; while long working hours, role ambiguity, and limitations in career development can negatively affect this quality.

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1. Introduction

Working life encompasses a significant portion of individuals' lives and has economic, social, and psychological dimensions. Therefore, employees' experiences in the workplace directly affect not only their individual well-being but also the productivity, performance, and sustainability of organizations. In this context, approaches aimed at improving employee well-being and satisfaction have gained increasing importance for organizations in recent years, and the concept of quality of working life has become a significant research area in academic literature.

Quality of working life is a multidimensional concept that refers to the physical, psychological, and social well-being of employees in the work environment. Walton (1973) addressed quality of working life within a broad framework encompassing elements such as fair wages, safe working conditions, opportunities for individual development, job security, organizational participation, and social integration. This approach demonstrates that quality of working life is not limited solely to economic factors; it is also shaped by the interaction of factors such as organizational structure, working conditions, career opportunities, and work-life balance. The literature frequently emphasizes that quality of working life has significant effects on employee satisfaction, organizational commitment, job performance, and employee well-being (Sirgy et al., 2001). Improving working conditions can increase employee commitment to the organization, strengthen job satisfaction, and reduce employee turnover (Hackman & Oldham, 1976). Especially in modern working life, increasing competition, technological transformation, and changing work models necessitate a more comprehensive approach to the concept of quality of working life. In this context, work-life balance, career development, organizational support, communication environment, and wage policies are among the key determinants of quality of working life (Bakker & Demerouti, 2007).

Human resources professionals are one of the key actors shaping employee experience in organizations. They are responsible for implementing practices that directly impact employee experience, such as recruitment, performance appraisal, career management, training, and development. Therefore, human resources professionals are not only actors who manage organizational processes but also employees who are directly involved in these processes. The strategic human

resources management literature emphasizes that human resources professionals play a central role in shaping employee experience, performance management, and the implementation of corporate policies in organizations (Ulrich, 1997; Wright & McMahan, 2011). However, a review of the literature reveals that research on quality of working life largely focuses on general employee groups or specific sectors. Studies directly examining human resources professionals' perceptions of quality of working life are limited. Yet, because human resources professionals play a central role in regulating working conditions and managing employee experience in organizations, they are both implementers and experiencers of quality of working life. This situation highlights a significant research gap in the literature regarding the examination of human resources professionals' perceptions of their quality of working life (Boxall & Purcell, 2016; Guest, 2017).

The main objective of this research is to reveal the perceptions of human resources professionals regarding their quality of working life and to identify the organizational factors that shape this perception. Accordingly, the research aims to examine human resources professionals' perceptions of their quality of working life and the factors influencing this perception, such as job security, work-life balance, career opportunities, organizational communication, and wage policies. Within this scope, the research seeks answers to the following questions:

- What are human resources professionals' perceptions of quality of working life?
- What organizational factors affect quality of working life?
- How are experiences related to work-life balance, career opportunities, and compensation policies shaped?
- How do organizational climate, communication, and participation mechanisms affect quality of working life?

2. Literature Review

2.1. The Concept of Quality of Working Life

Work, beyond being an economic activity, is a life experience that affects individuals' social identity, daily routines, and social relationships, and can either support or limit their personal development. Experiences gained in working life shape an individual's life outside of work. In this context, the quality of working life becomes a determining factor in individual well-being (Martel & Dupuis, 2006; Jayakumar & Kalaiselvi, 2012).

The concept of quality of working life is considered in the literature as a multidimensional approach encompassing the entirety of employees' perceptions of

their work experiences and work environment. Employees evaluate the content and conditions of their work not only in terms of "objective" characteristics but also perceptually in light of their own expectations, needs, and experiences. Therefore, criteria related to working life are subjective (Pillai & Ramakrishnan, 2024). What constitutes a quality/good working life can vary depending on variables such as age, career stage, sector, and position within the organization (Kiernan & Knutson, 1990). Employees' perceptions can also influence their decisions to join, stay in, or leave an organization (Bagtasos, 2011: 4-6).

In a narrow sense, quality of working life is associated with an employee finding meaning in their work and deriving positive emotions from it; in a broader sense, it corresponds to a framework encompassing the quality of employment and all direct/indirect conditions of working life. Within this broad framework, elements such as the ethics and safety of work and employment, job security and equal treatment, wages and non-wage benefits, working hours, work-life balance, social protection, social dialogue, training and skills development, workplace relations, and work motivation stand out (Erdoğan & Durmuşkaya, 2017). Kiernan and Knutson (1990), on the other hand, emphasize that quality of working life should not be seen only as a set of services or fringe benefits provided by the employer; it corresponds to a dynamic relationship area that develops within the interaction between employee and employer. Since individuals' needs and expectations change over time, the meaning attributed to work also differs according to age, income level, personal life responsibilities, and personal goals (Kiernan & Knutson, 1990).

Quality of working life can take on different layers of meaning depending on the perspective of stakeholders: For managers, it is associated with productivity and efficiency goals through employee participation in decision-making processes and improvements in the psychological aspects of work; while for unions and employees, it can be expressed through expectations such as fairer income distribution, job security, and healthy working conditions (Walton, 1973). In general, quality of working life is a holistic term encompassing the emotional and cognitive components of work experience, such as wages, safety, healthy working conditions, job security, participation, development opportunities, work-life balance, and social relationships.

2.2. Key Factors Affecting Quality of Working Life

Quality of working life is a multidimensional construct shaped by the interaction of numerous factors at both individual and organizational levels. Literature indicates that determinants influencing quality of working life include elements such as wage and reward systems, the nature and meaning of work, working conditions, occupational health and safety, job security, organizational justice, leadership style, organizational climate, and social support. Working hours, workload, stress level, and work-life balance are also considered fundamental components of quality of working life. In this context, variables such as personal

characteristics, individuals' psychological state, job satisfaction, workplace stress, and perception of justice are closely related to quality of working life (Walton, 1973).

In recent years, work-life balance and quality of working life have become particularly prominent in studies. It has been reported that flexible and remote working practices, which became widespread in the post-pandemic period, have increased job satisfaction and overall life satisfaction in some employee groups, and have also reduced burnout levels. However, it is also argued that flexibility does not produce the same results in every context; factors such as workload, role ambiguity, and the expectation of constant availability can strain the boundaries of work-life balance. Bagtasos (2011), emphasizing the multidimensionality of quality of working life, highlights dimensions such as work-family balance, skill level, autonomy, difficulty level of the job, job security and stress, management style, physical conditions, occupational health and safety, working hours, nature of the job, incentive opportunities, and collaboration (Bagtasos, 2011: 3).

The importance of quality of working life is further highlighted by its effects on employee job satisfaction, engagement, performance, work alienation, and intention to leave. The financial and non-financial resources that organizations provide to employees can contribute to meeting not only economic needs but also health, safety, and social needs. Meeting these needs can not only increase job satisfaction but also support satisfaction in other areas of an individual's life, thus affecting their overall quality of life (Sirgy et al., 2001: 277–278). In this respect, quality of working life is considered not only related to the work environment but also as a concept that touches upon an individual's holistic life experience.

2.3. Quality of Working Life in the Context of Human Resources Professionals

Human resources (HR) departments are at the center of processes such as recruitment and placement, performance management, compensation and benefits, training and development, employee relations, labor law practices, and organizational policy design. This position requires HR professionals to interact intensely with both employees and senior management; it can create time pressure, high responsibility, and expectations of constant problem-solving. Due to the nature of the HR role, experiences such as being caught between employee expectations and organizational priorities, emotional labor, role conflict, and ethical dilemmas may arise. This suggests that HR professionals' perceptions of their quality of working life are shaped not only by classical factors (salary, duration, physical conditions, etc.) but also by more "relational" and "psychological" dimensions such as role dynamics, fairness, and meaningfulness (Ulrich, 1997; Guest & Conway, 2011; Hochschild, 1983).

This study examines the quality of working life of HR professionals through the following axes: (i) legal security and perception of employment (compliance

with legislation, job security, and union perspective), (ii) work arrangements and work-life balance (hybrid work experience, long working hours, and the paradox of flexibility), (iii) organizational climate and career management (participation in decision-making, fairness and criteria in promotion processes), and (iv) the meaning of work and economic satisfaction (intrinsic motivation sources, wage satisfaction, and inflationary pressures). Thus, the aim is to holistically understand how HR professionals experience their working conditions and which factors they consider decisive in terms of quality of working life.

3. Methodology

The study's working group consisted of participants holding managerial positions in the human resources departments of businesses operating in various sectors in Istanbul, Turkey. Participants were reached using the snowball sampling technique, a non-probability sampling method, and a total of 14 human resources professionals were interviewed. In accordance with the qualitative research design, the sample size was determined by considering the principle of data saturation. The data collection process was terminated when the data obtained during the interviews began to repeat around certain themes and did not provide new conceptual contributions. This approach supports the internal validity of the study and the in-depth analysis of the findings. Demographic information about the participants is presented in the table below.

Table 1: Demographic Characteristics of Participants

Participant	Gender	Age	Education	Sector	Task
Participant 1	Female	39	Bachelor's Degree-Economics	Call Center	Payroll Manager
Participant 2	Male	28	Bachelor's Degree-Business Administration	Call Center	Organizational Development Unit Manager
Participant 3	Male	40	Bachelor's Degree-Finance Master's Degree-Human Resources	Energy	Human Resources Manager
Participant 4	Male	42	Bachelor's Degree-Labor Economics and Industrial Relations	Banking	Personnel and Employment Manager
Participant 5	Female	31	Bachelor's Degree-Economics Master's Degree-Human Resources Management	Pharmaceutical	Human Resources Manager
Participant 6	Female	41	Bachelor's Degree-Classical Philology, Master's Degree-Human Resources Management	Energy	Human Resources Partner
Participant 7	Female	34	Bachelor's Degree-History of Science Master's Degree-Human Resources Management	Maritime	Human Resources Manager

Participant 8	Male	38	Bachelor's Degree-Labor Economics and Industrial Relations Master's Degree-Management and Organization	Technology	Human Resources and Administrative Affairs Manager
Participant 9	Male	54	Bachelor's Degree-Tourism and Hotel Management	Aviation	Human Resources Director
Participant 10	Male	55	Bachelor's Degree-Business Administration	Packaging	Human Resources Manager
Participant 11	Female	46	Bachelor's Degree-Business Administration, Master's Degree-Human Resources Management / Psychology	Communications	Human Resources Chief
Participant 12	Female	38	Bachelor's Degree-Labor Economics and Industrial Relations	Cosmetics	Human Resources Chief
Participant 13	Female	33	Bachelor's Degree-Labor Economics and Industrial Relations Master's Degree-Human Resources Management	Transportation	Human Resources Chief
Participant 14	Male	35	Bachelor's Degree-Labor Economics and Industrial Relations	Food	Human Resources Partner

Source: Created by the authors.

In this study, data were collected using a semi-structured interview method. Interviews were conducted between May 2024 and December 2025. Participants requested that the interviews be conducted online due to their busy work schedules; therefore, the interviews were conducted via Microsoft Teams and Zoom platforms, and each interview lasted an average of 45–60 minutes. Before the interviews began, the purpose and scope of the research were explained to the participants, and their informed consent was obtained on a voluntary basis. Participants were informed that the interviews would be recorded and were given the necessary information regarding data privacy. To protect the identities of the participants, the interview data was stored in a way that was only accessible to the researchers, and the participants were anonymized using codes such as P1 and P2. Observation notes on the participants' gestures, facial expressions, and emotional states, as well as field diaries, were also kept during the interviews. Before commencing the field research, the necessary ethical approval was obtained from the Istanbul Arel University Ethics Committee (Decision No: E-52857131-050.04-790797; dated 20.02.2026 and numbered 2026/04).

The qualitative data obtained in the research were analyzed using the thematic analysis method. Thematic analysis is a flexible analytical approach that allows for the systematic identification of recurring patterns of meaning within the data (Braun & Clarke, 2006). The data analysis process was carried out in several stages. In the first stage, the interview recordings were transcribed in detail by the first author. Then, all researchers reread the texts to familiarize themselves with the dataset and make preliminary assessments regarding the patterns of meaning within the data. Subsequently, the interview transcripts were transferred to the MAXQDA

2020 program, and the systematic coding process was initiated. In the coding phase, the dataset was examined line by line, initial codes were created, and similar codes were grouped together to identify potential themes. The generated codes and themes were re-evaluated by the research team, the relationships between the themes were examined, and they were reviewed in terms of conceptual integrity. As a result of evaluation meetings held among the researchers, a common consensus was reached regarding the coding and theme creation process. In the final stage, the themes were reviewed again, and a consensus was reached on the scope and naming of the themes. At the end of this process, the research findings were classified under six main themes: legal security and perception of employment, work arrangements and work-life balance, career management and fairness, organizational climate and participation, nature of work and qualifications match, and wage policy and economic satisfaction.

The research has some limitations. Firstly, the study was conducted only with human resources professionals working in businesses operating in Istanbul, Turkey. This may limit the generalizability of the findings to different cities or cultural contexts. Secondly, the research was conducted using a qualitative research method with a limited number of participants. While the aim of qualitative research is to develop an in-depth understanding rather than generalization, quantitative studies with larger samples could contribute to supporting the findings. Finally, since the data were obtained through semi-structured interviews, the participants' subjective evaluations and individual experiences shaped the dataset. Nevertheless, the study offers important findings in terms of examining the quality of working life of human resources professionals from a multidimensional perspective.

4. Findings

This research examines the experiences of human resources professionals regarding their quality of working life from a multidimensional perspective, revealing the effects of organizational working conditions on employee experiences. The research findings show that the quality of working life is shaped not only by material factors such as wages and economic conditions, but also by the interaction of numerous organizational elements such as organizational climate, career opportunities, role structure, and work-life balance.

One of the key findings of the study is that legal security and organizational structures create a strong sense of trust for employees. A large majority of participants stated that compliance with labor law, the existence of written procedures, and organizational processes protected employee rights. This indicates that organizational structures play a significant role in employees' perception of psychological security and quality of working life. Findings regarding work arrangements and work-life balance reveal that hybrid work models have a twofold impact on employee experiences. On the one hand, hybrid work practices enable employees to gain spatial flexibility and dedicate more time to their personal lives,

while on the other hand, factors such as the expectation of constant availability and the uncertainty of working hours can negatively affect work-life balance. This finding shows that flexible work models do not always improve employee well-being and can invisibly increase workload in some cases. The research also reveals that career management and perceptions of organizational justice have a significant impact on the quality of working life. While some participants stated that their organizations have criteria-based promotion systems, others highlighted the presence of uncertainty and subjective practices in promotion processes. This indicates that transparency and merit-based practices in career management processes are critical for employee motivation. In terms of organizational climate and participation, open communication channels and accessibility to managers are seen as positive factors for employees. However, the limited number of social activities and the presence of social barriers, such as group formation in some cases point to areas that need improvement in terms of organizational commitment and social integration. Finally, the findings regarding wage policy and economic satisfaction show that employees' perceptions of wage policies are heterogeneous. While some participants evaluated performance-based wage systems positively, others stated that the perception of fairness could be weakened due to imbalances in wage distribution and a lack of criteria.

To visualize the density and conceptual distribution of the codes obtained in the thematic analysis process within the dataset, a code cloud was created in Figure 1 below. Examination of the code cloud reveals that concepts such as work-life balance (positive), salary satisfaction, job security, and job-person/skill fit stand out in the perception of working life quality among human resources professionals. This finding indicates that participants, when evaluating working life quality, attach importance not only to economic factors but also to multidimensional factors such as the compatibility of the job with individual competencies, a sense of security, and work organization. Another noteworthy element in the code cloud is the significant role of concepts such as skill-oriented development, compliance with labor laws, and criteria-based promotion. This reveals that organizational structures and processes play a decisive role in employees' perceptions of working life quality. However, the presence of concepts such as work-life balance (negative), long working hours, role ambiguity, and lack of criteria in salary in the dataset shows that working life quality is not solely composed of positive experiences, and that some structural and organizational problems can also affect employee experience.

Figure 1: Code Cloud

Source: Created by the authors via MAXQDA.

In the qualitative data analysis process, the interview data obtained were systematically examined in accordance with the thematic analysis approach developed by Braun and Clarke (2006).

Table 2: Main Themes and Subcodes Obtained from Thematic Analysis

Main Theme	Subcodes	Definition / Scope
1. Legal Security and Employment Perception	Compliance with Labor Laws	Ensuring the institution fully complies with legal regulations and that rights are protected.
	The Existence of Job Security	The absence of fear of being laid off, and the perception of employment sustainability.
	Negative Views on Unionization	White-collar workers may have a distant attitude towards union structures or view them as unnecessary.

Main Theme	Subcodes	Definition / Scope
2. Work Schedule and Work-Life Balance	Corporate Awareness	The sense of security provided by the company's corporate structure.
	Lack of Unionization	The absence of a union organization in the workplace.
		Working Hours, Flexibility, and The Impact of Work on Personal Life.
	Hybrid / Remote Work	Implementation of a location-independent or hybrid work model.
	Work-Life Balance (Positive)	Achieving balance between work and personal life.
	Work-Life Imbalance (Negative)	Work encroaching on personal life, the problem of not being able to find time.
3. Career Management and Justice	Long Working Hours	Working long hours beyond the legal deadlines.
	Standard (Full-Time) Employment	The classic office-based work schedule.
		Promotion Processes, Meritocracy, And Perceptions Of Development Opportunities.
	Promotion Based on Criteria	Promotion Processes Should Be Subject To Specific And Transparent Rules.
	Quality-Oriented Development	The availability of training and support that will enhance professional competence.
4. Organizational Climate and Participation	Arbitrariness in Promotions	Subjective decisions or uncertainty prevail in promotion processes.
	Lack of Focus on Development	The organization fails to support the employee's personal development.
	Valuing Ideas	Taking opinions into account in decision-making processes and open communication.

Main Theme	Subcodes	Definition / Scope
	Open Communication Channels	Uninterrupted communication between management and employees.
	Adequacy of Physical Conditions	Office environment, ergonomics, and adequacy of equipment.
	Limited Social Event	Insufficient opportunities for internal socialization within the organization.
5. Nature of The Job And Qualification Match		The Content of The Work, The Person's Skills, and Their Level of Satisfaction.
	Job-Person (Qualification) Match	The employee's skills must match the job requirements.
	Task Clarity	Clearly defined roles and responsibilities.
	Role Ambiguity	Confusion in job descriptions.
	Multitask	The HR manager needs to oversee multiple areas of expertise.
6. Wage Policy and Economic Satisfaction		Financial Rewards, Benefits, and the Impact of Economic Conditions.
	Benefits	Material/in-kind benefits provided in addition to salary.
	Salary Satisfaction	The perception that the wage received covers the labor and needs.
	Criteria-Based Compensation	Salary increases should be determined based on performance/market conditions.
	Inflationary Pressure	Dissatisfaction stemming from macroeconomic conditions that have reduced purchasing power.
	Lack of Criteria in Wage Determination	Lack of transparency or relationship-based processes in wage setting.

Source: Created by the authors.

In line with the themes presented in Table 2, the perceptions and experiences of human resources professionals regarding the quality of their working lives are evaluated in detail below, along with participant opinions within each main theme.

4.3. Theme 1: Legal Security and Employment Perceptions

4.3.1. Compliance with Labor Law

The interview findings indicate that one of the determining factors in the quality of working life for human resources professionals is the high level of compliance with the Labor Law No. 4857 within the organization. Participants emphasized that one of the fundamental functions of the human resources unit is to ensure compliance with legislation. The conduct of leave, payroll, wage, contract, and termination processes in accordance with the legal framework and in a manner open to scrutiny was considered by participants as a significant indicator of organizational security. The intensity of audits by the Social Security Institution and inspections, in particular, points to the establishment of a protective and systematic approach to preventing legal risks within the organizations. Furthermore, the active functioning of the legal unit, audit processes conducted within the scope of quality standards, and meticulousness in occupational health and safety practices demonstrate that compliance with legislation is not only a legal obligation but also a structural element supporting role clarity, organizational predictability, and quality of working life (Walton, 1973; International Labour Organization [ILO], 2016).

One participant described the situation as follows:

“So my main reason for being here is to protect Law No. 4857... from leave processes to employee salary situations, payroll processes, and contract processes, we work completely using the powers granted by the law.” (Participant 2).

Similarly, another participant emphasized workplace safety and inspection processes, *“I am satisfied with my company in terms of quality management standards. It provides all the necessary comfort conditions and occupational safety,” (Participant 3) stated.*

4.3.2. Existence of Job Security

The findings reveal that human resources professionals generally perceive job security as high. Participants define job security primarily through the absence of anxiety about unjustified dismissal and the perception of sustainable employment. Organizations focusing on protecting and developing their human resources rather than losing them, adopting an approach aimed at resolving employee problems, and limiting dismissal processes to exceptional circumstances, all contribute to a strong sense of security. In this context, job security can be considered not only a legal protection mechanism but also a component of working life reinforced by psychological security, organizational stability, and mutual trust (Greenhalgh & Rosenblatt, 1984; Kahn, 1990).

One participant described the situation with the following words:

“Job security essentially means that employees can continue working without worrying about losing their jobs today or tomorrow... and we offer this to all our employees at our company.” (Participant 10).

Similarly, statements from other participants support this perception:

“I never had any concerns about job security” (Participant 6);

“We don’t have anything like the fear of losing our jobs or the fear of losing our rights.” (Participant 8).

4.3.3. Negative Views on Unionization

Research findings indicate that human resources professionals' attitudes towards unionization are predominantly negative. Participants believe that more rights and gains can be achieved within the existing corporate structure than through unionization, and therefore often view union organization as an unnecessary tool. The correlation established between wage increase rates and union dues reinforces the perception that unions do not produce a clear benefit for employees. Furthermore, some participants view union structures as cost-increasing, reducing flexibility, and sometimes susceptible to instrumentalization. This situation demonstrates that the perception of security among white-collar human resources professionals is based more on corporate protection and knowledge of individual rights than on collective organization (Freeman & Medoff, 1984; Bryson et al., 2010).

This approach is clearly demonstrated in the words of one participant:

“So if I were to come here to the union right now, I probably wouldn’t be here. Because I think I’ve received something better than what the union would demand for me.” (Participant 1).

Another participant offered a more critical assessment:

“I don’t have a very positive view... I have a negative view on the union issue... I don’t think they provide much support to the staff either.” (Participant 2).

Similarly,

The statement, *“Union membership doesn’t make much sense to me... I know my rights and I am capable of protecting them.” (Participant 14)*, also reveals the relationship between knowledge of individual rights and the distance felt towards unions.

4.3.4. Corporate Awareness

Participants' statements indicate that the level of corporate awareness and institutionalization positively affects the quality of working life of human resources professionals. Participants stated that working in well-established and reputable organizations strengthens feelings of trust, belonging, prestige, and organizational stability. In particular, the presence of employees who have worked at the same institution for many years, low turnover rates, and open communication channels within the organization demonstrate that the corporate structure creates a sense of

trust among employees. The fact that the institution does not view its employees as merely personnel numbers supports feelings of belonging and being valued. In this context, corporate awareness can be considered an important element that generates trust and organizational commitment in the quality of working life of human resources professionals (Ashforth & Mael, 1989; Meyer & Allen, 1991).

One participant described the situation as follows:

"I see it as a good thing, we're like a family here... and because we're not a very big company, employees and managers can easily reach each other. Our doors are always open." (Participant 1).

Similarly, another participant said,

"I feel 100% a part of it... I see this very strongly in terms of company management and corporate identity, and loyalty to the logo." (Participant 7) emphasized belonging and corporate identification.

4.3.5. Lack of Unionization

The findings indicate that the human resources specialists included in the study mostly work in workplaces where unionization is absent. Participants generally perceive the lack of union membership as normal and compatible with the corporate structure. The absence of a significant demand or need for unionization, particularly among white-collar workers, reinforces the perception that existing working conditions and corporate practices compensate for the lack of unionization. Therefore, the absence of unionization is not interpreted by participants as a direct indicator of insecurity, but rather as a structure compatible with the current management approach (Kochan et al., 1986; Bryson, 2003).

This situation was also reflected in the participants' statements:

"There is no unionization... there is no union structure at the moment." (Participant 14);

"No, no, there is no union." (Participant 8).

Overall, the findings under the theme of legal security and employment perception show that the fundamental elements shaping the quality of working life for human resources professionals revolve around compliance with legislation, job security, institutional stability, and a sense of trust. Conversely, the hesitant attitude towards unionization and the absence of union organization reveal that security in this profession is defined more through institutional structure and knowledge of individual rights. In this respect, the theme demonstrates that the legal and institutional framework plays a central role in the quality of working life for human resources professionals.

4.4. Theme 2: Work Schedule and Work-Life Balance

4.4.1. Hybrid Operation

Interview data indicate that the hybrid work model is a significant determinant of human resources professionals' perception of quality of work life. Participants' statements reveal that the possibility of working from home on certain days of the week, remote access options, and flexible time management have positive effects on work-life balance. In particular, the ability to work remotely, conduct business from different cities, and dedicate more time to family life contribute to employees managing their professional and personal lives in a more balanced way.

However, the impact of the hybrid model varies depending on its implementation. While flexibility is considered a positive experience in structures where working days can be determined by employee initiative, the perception of autonomy weakens and satisfaction decreases in situations where mandatory office attendance increases, or the hybrid model is applied in a limited way. Furthermore, the inability to effectively utilize annual leave due to intensive work processes such as payroll periods and overtime shows that workload pressure can persist despite the hybrid model. Conversely, some organizations providing home-office infrastructure support and offering remote working opportunities contribute to employees gaining spatial flexibility and managing their family responsibilities more easily. These findings demonstrate that not only the existence of the hybrid work model, but also its implementation method and employee autonomy are decisive factors in work-life balance (Allen et al., 2015; Gajendran & Harrison, 2007).

One participant expressed the flexibility offered by hybrid work with the following words:

"I can take time off whenever I want, I can work from home whenever I want. I can dedicate time to myself on weekends." (Participant 2).

Similarly, another participant described the hybrid model as follows:

"We work from home two days a week... I can say it's a pretty good system considering the conditions in Istanbul." (Participant 12).

4.4.2. Work-Life Balance (Positive)

The findings indicate that a significant portion of human resources professionals have positive experiences regarding work-life balance. Participants stated that they were able to achieve a balance between work and private life thanks to flexible working arrangements, reasonable working hours, and weekends generally being dedicated to non-work time. Remote work opportunities, mobile work possibilities, and the digitalization of work processes also facilitate employees' ability to plan their personal lives. In particular, limited working hours and the rarity of weekend work allow employees to dedicate time to their families and personal interests. This is considered an important factor supporting the quality of working life (Greenhaus & Allen, 2011; Kossek et al., 2011).

One participant described the situation as follows:

“I think my work-life balance is good... I can make time for my hobbies.”
(Participant 1).

Similarly, another participant made the following assessment:

“We work 7.5–8 hours a day, with no work on weekends. This allows me to have time for myself.” (Participant 2).

4.4.3. Work-Life Imbalance (Negative)

However, some participants noted that work-life balance is not always maintained and that the expectation of constant availability, especially with a heavy workload, negatively impacts personal life. Bringing work home, continuing work demands in the evenings or on weekends, and the need to be constantly online limit employees' personal time. Furthermore, managers' inability to adequately maintain working hours during remote work can make it difficult for employees to manage their time effectively (Greenhaus & Beutell, 1985; Derks & Bakker, 2014).

One participant expressed the situation as follows:

“Because we have remote work days, managers sometimes lose track of working hours. The demands that come in the evenings and on weekends make it difficult to strike a balance.” (Participant 9).

Similarly, another participant stated the following:

“It's very bad, I have no work-life balance. I spend most of my life at work.”
(Participant 3).

These findings suggest that hybrid and remote work practices can negatively impact work-life balance when not implemented with appropriate organizational boundaries and managerial support.

4.4.4. Long Working Hours

Research findings indicate that human resources specialists may face long working hours due to heavy workloads and broad responsibilities. Simultaneously managing payroll, performance, and operational processes can require employees to remain constantly online. Insufficient staffing levels and the breadth of departmental responsibilities lead to workloads exceeding legally mandated working hours (Sparks et al., 1997; Caruso, 2014).

One participant described the situation with the following words:

“We have no concept of time... even on weekends, the computer is always with us.” (Participant 4).

Similarly, another participant described their workload as follows:

“I work intensely... you constantly have to produce something and follow every process.” (Participant 13).

This shows that long working hours can have limiting effects on work-life balance and social life.

4.4.5. Standard (Full-Time) Work

Interview findings indicate that in some organizations, human resources specialists still work in an office-centric and standard full-time schedule. Fixed weekly working hours of 42–45 hours, especially long office hours spread across mornings and evenings, can limit employees' personal time. Those working in organizations with limited options for working from home or flexible working arrangements may experience greater difficulties in planning their lives outside of work (Kalleberg, 2009; Golden, 2009).

One participant described the study routine as follows:

“Our office hours are from 9 am to 6 pm.” (Participant 1).

Another participant explained the situation with the following words:

“We work 45 hours a week... That’s about 9 hours a day.” (Participant 5).

Overall, the findings regarding work arrangements and work-life balance indicate that flexible working practices and digital work opportunities positively impact the quality of working life for human resources professionals. However, hybrid working models can weaken work-life balance if appropriate managerial boundaries and workload balance are not ensured, and the expectation of constant accessibility can limit employees' personal lives. Therefore, in terms of quality of working life, not only the existence of flexible working models but also their balanced implementation with organizational support and workload management is critically important.

4.5. Theme 3: Career Management and Justice

4.5.1. Promotion Based on Criteria

The interview findings indicate that organizational procedures and specific criteria play a significant role in human resources professionals' perceptions of career management and promotion processes. Participants state that promotion processes are conducted based on objective criteria such as education level, professional experience, certifications, foreign language proficiency, and performance evaluation results. The planned evaluation of promotion decisions at specific periods and the involvement of committees consisting of the Human Resources unit and managers in the process indicate the existence of a systematic career structure in organizations. However, in some organizations, the fact that promotion processes are tied to specific time conditions can lead to situations where high-performing employees cannot be promoted in the short term. In particular, the obligation to work in the same position for a certain period can limit the speed of career advancement and create a stagnant effect on motivation. Nevertheless, overall assessments show that promotion processes are largely conducted within a merit- and criteria-based structure (Noe, 2017; Colquitt et al., 2001).

One participant described the promotion process as follows:

“There are criteria for the position to be promoted to... There is an interview process involving both the manager and human resources.” (Participant 1).

Similarly, another participant described the promotion system as follows:

“Evaluations are made based on individuals’ experience, education, certifications, and performance... Title changes are carried out periodically.” (Participant 3).

4.5.2. Arbitrariness in Promotions

Research findings indicate that despite the existence of formal criteria, promotion processes in some organizations are open to subjective evaluations. Participants state that a systematic career planning structure is not institutionalized in every organization, and in some cases, promotion decisions can be shaped by the individual evaluations of managers. In particular, the fact that performance appraisal systems are not based on measurable outcomes can weaken the objectivity of decisions. Participant statements show that, in the Turkish context, factors such as managerial support, referral relationships, or interventions from upper management can sometimes be influential in promotion processes. In addition, the limited number of senior positions and the narrow hierarchical structure in organizations can structurally restrict career advancement. This situation can create uncertainty and a weakening of the perception of fairness regarding career advancement among employees (Greenberg, 1990; Colquitt et al., 2001).

One participant described the situation with the following words:

“Promotion processes proceed according to the wishes of the managers... There are no specific rules or limits.” (Participant 9).

Another participant expressed concerns about trust issues related to promotion processes as follows:

“Some appointments can be arbitrary. In this case, faith in the promotion process weakens.” (Participant 12).

4.5.3. Inability to Focus on Development

The findings indicate that systematic practices supporting the professional and personal development of employees are not sufficiently institutionalized in some organizations. Participants state that training programs, career planning mechanisms, and talent management practices are limited in some organizations. Employee development may be relegated to the background, particularly due to factors such as economic downturns, restructuring processes, or changes in corporate priorities. While some participants noted that their previous organizational experiences included more structured career and training systems, they stated that these areas are weak in their current organizations. The cancellation of training budgets or the inability to sustainably implement development programs can increase the mismatch between employees' career expectations and corporate

practices. This situation can lead to individual development efforts being largely left to the employee's own initiative, resulting in decreased motivation (Garavan et al., 2012; Noe, 2017).

One participant described the situation as follows:

"I could have pursued a better career path, but these areas are a bit weak where I am." (Participant 4).

Another participant expressed the limited institutional support with the following words:

"I mostly try to create the conditions for my career development myself." (Participant 9).

4.5.4. Quality-Oriented Development

Research findings indicate that some organizations have training and support mechanisms aimed at developing professional competencies. In particular, in heavily regulated sectors, the continuity of professional training has become an institutional necessity. It is stated that employees in operational units such as cabin crew, cockpit crew, or technical personnel are subject to periodic training and certification processes. However, it is observed that development opportunities are more limited for white-collar employees and progress is often based on individual effort. While some organizations have practices such as postgraduate support, professional certification funding, or foreign language training, it is understood that strategic systems supporting employees' career development holistically are not institutionalized to the same extent in every organization (Noe, 2017; Garavan et al., 2012).

One participant described the vocational training processes as follows:

"Cabin crew and technical staff have regular training sessions that are monitored by the training department." (Participant 1).

Another participant described the organization's training support as follows:

"We support some employees in pursuing postgraduate studies or professional certifications." (Participant 3).

Overall, the findings obtained within the scope of career management and justice show that promotion processes in organizations are mostly conducted within a criteria-based framework. However, in some organizations, managerial interventions, limited promotion opportunities, and a lack of systematic career planning can weaken employees' perception of organizational justice. Furthermore, it is observed that professional development opportunities vary depending on sectoral requirements, and development processes are more limited, especially for white-collar employees. This situation reveals that career management is closely related not only to promotion processes but also to the systematicity and accessibility of development opportunities offered to employees.

4.6. Theme 4: Organizational Climate and Participation

4.6.1. Valuing Ideas

The research findings indicate that the sub-theme of valuing opinions within the context of organizational climate and participation is generally associated with a positive perception. Participants stated that they had access to senior management, felt relatively free to express their views, and that managers exhibited an open attitude towards criticism. The existence of suggestion boxes, digital notification systems, and similar mechanisms within the organization shows that employee opinions can be conveyed through formal channels. This indicates that organizational participation is supported at the procedural level. However, it is also understood that there is not always a direct relationship between receiving opinions and their reflection in decision-making processes. Participants stated that some suggestions could not be implemented due to cost, feasibility, security, or structural limitations. Furthermore, a comparative perception is noteworthy: access to senior management is easier in small and medium-sized organizations, while it may be more limited in large and corporate structures. In this context, the perception of valuing opinions should be evaluated not only in terms of the existence of communication channels but also in terms of the impact of these channels on decision-making mechanisms (Morrison, 2011; Schneider et al., 2013).

One participant expressed this situation as *“Ideas are always taken into consideration.”* (Participant 1), while another participant supported this perception by saying, *“One’s opinion is considered, we have a suggestion box.”* (Participant 3). Similarly, the statement, *“Even if my idea won’t be accepted, it is listened to with value.”* (Participant 7) shows that employees have at least a strong perception that they are being listened to.

4.6.2. Open Communication Channels

The findings indicate that open communication channels are perceived as one of the key determinants of organizational climate. Participants stated that hierarchical barriers between management and employees are relatively low, access to upper management is possible, and an "open door" approach is adopted. Especially in family-owned businesses, long-term employment relationships and strong personal ties create a foundation for more sincere and direct communication. The fact that employees are not seen merely as "personnel numbers" stands out as a factor that strengthens the sense of belonging. Participants' statements show that open communication is valued not only in management-employee relations but also in inter-employee relations. Team solidarity, mutual support, and social interaction can serve a balancing function, especially in intense and demanding work processes. However, it is understood that the perception of open communication may vary depending on variables such as the size of the organization, ownership

structure, sector, and the individual's position within the organization. Therefore, while open communication is an important factor that positively affects the quality of working life, it is not considered a sufficient determinant on its own (Men, 2014; Schneider et al., 2013).

One participant summarized this perception by saying, *“Our employer is good, our work environment is good, and we have very good communication with upper management.”* (Participant 1). Another participant emphasized the multifaceted nature of communication channels by stating, *“There are many channels through which employees can reach HR and managers... There is an environment where they can discuss all their complaints and requests for improvement directly.”* (Participant 14).

4.6.3. Adequacy of Physical Conditions

Research findings indicate that the perception of the adequacy of physical conditions is generally positive. Participants stated that they did not experience any significant deficiencies in terms of office environment, ergonomic equipment, and technical equipment; and that the necessary tools and equipment were mostly provided quickly. This suggests that organizations adopt a sensitive approach to providing the necessary physical infrastructure for employees to perform their jobs effectively (Vischer, 2007). However, it is also observed that physical working conditions differ depending on the sector. While ergonomics and equipment adequacy are prioritized for office workers, physical conditions for those working in technical or operational fields are determined by the nature of the work. Furthermore, the fact that some participants preferred shared areas despite having individual office spaces shows that physical space is important not only for comfort but also for communication and collaboration. In this context, physical conditions act as a "hygiene factor" in terms of quality of working life; although it does not produce high satisfaction on its own, it is considered a fundamental element that can create dissatisfaction if it is lacking (Herzberg, 1966).

One participant stated, *“In our company, support such as desks, chairs, computers, and phones are provided quickly; I don't experience any physical deficiencies.”* (Participant 2). Similarly, the statement, *“Our physical work environment is very good... It is adequate in terms of lighting, air conditioning, and equipment.”* (Participant 12) also supports this positive perception.

4.6.4. Limited Social Activities

Participants' statements reveal that internal social activities are limited and inadequate. It appears that existing activities are mostly limited to infrequent events such as New Year's celebrations, Iftar dinners, or seniority award ceremonies. This situation is considered insufficient for strengthening social bonds among employees and supporting organizational belonging (Kahn, 1990).

Some participants stated that insufficient physical space and limited internal social environments negatively impacted opportunities for socialization. Furthermore, the presence of social barriers such as insincerity, cliques, and exclusion can make the integration process more difficult, especially for new employees. Although open communication channels exist between managers and employees, a more relaxed and secure social interaction environment is not sufficiently developed. These findings indicate that social activities and organizational culture are among the areas that need improvement in terms of employee engagement and organizational climate (Bakker & Demerouti, 2007).

One participant highlighted the limited social activities, stating, *“Apart from the classic New Year’s event, the Iftar dinner, and the one-off seniority awards ceremony, there aren’t many other events.”* (Participant 3). Similarly, the statement, *“Social activities are definitely insufficient and could be improved.”* (Participant 5), also points to a weakness in corporate social life.

Overall, the findings obtained within the scope of organizational climate and participation indicate that open communication channels, accessibility to management, and opportunities to express opinions positively affect the quality of working life. However, the level of influence of opinions on decision-making processes, the limited social activities, and certain organizational dynamics that weaken social integration show that this positive structure is lacking in complementary elements. Therefore, organizational climate should be considered not only in terms of communication openness but also in conjunction with the effectiveness of participation, social integration, and the level of organizational support.

4.7. Theme 5: Job Nature and Qualification Fit

4.7.1. Job-Person (Qualification) Match

Research findings indicate that a significant portion of human resources professionals perceive a high level of alignment between their work and their competencies. Participants stated that their social competencies, such as communication skills, empathy, organizational ability, and interpersonal management, align with the requirements of the human resources profession. In addition, technical knowledge and analytical skills related to payroll, reporting, regulatory compliance, and financial processes were also noted as playing a significant role in the execution of the job.

Participants' statements indicate that individual interests and competencies are decisive in career choice, and that experiences gained over time further strengthen this alignment. The multifaceted and dynamic nature of the job supports employees' professional development by offering opportunities to manage different tasks and solve problems, and has positive effects on job satisfaction. These findings reveal that the alignment between employees' competencies and the

requirements of the job is a significant determinant of both job satisfaction and organizational performance (Edwards, 1991; Kristof-Brown et al., 2005).

One participant expressed this agreement as follows:

“To work in human resources, you need strong communication skills and well-developed empathy... Over time, I realized that my personal qualities were compatible with this job.” (Participant 1).

Similarly, another participant noted the compatibility between their job and personal characteristics, stating, *“I enjoy communicating with people, and my job reflects this aspect of myself” (Participant 3).*

4.7.2. Task Clarity

Research findings indicate that job descriptions are defined in a written and systematic manner in many organizations. Participants stated that job descriptions clearly define authority, responsibility, and areas of duty, and that employees are informed about the roles and expectations required by their positions. Presenting job descriptions to employees, especially during the recruitment process, and recording them in their personnel files ensures that role expectations are clearly defined. Furthermore, it was noted that in some organizations, job descriptions are regularly updated, and employees' individual goals and departmental goals can be tracked through the system. This contributes to employees understanding their duties more clearly and to the more efficient execution of work processes (Kahn et al., 1964; Rizzo et al., 1970).

One participant described the situation with the following words:

“Job descriptions are clear and in writing. Authorities, areas of responsibility, and position requirements are clearly defined.” (Participant 1).

Similarly, another participant stated that the job descriptions were created systematically, saying:

“Job descriptions for both blue-collar and white-collar personnel are prepared in detail.” (Participant 11).

4.7.3. Role Ambiguity

Despite the existence of job descriptions, some participants stated that role ambiguity and task confusion could occur in practice. Participants indicated that in some cases, job descriptions were not sufficiently clear, forcing them to undertake responsibilities outside of those descriptions. This situation can be more pronounced in organizations where institutionalization processes are not yet complete. The necessity of performing the duties of multiple positions simultaneously increases the workload of employees and can lead to a blurring of job boundaries. This weakens employees' sense of role and can sometimes negatively impact motivation and job satisfaction (Kahn et al., 1964; Rizzo et al., 1970).

One participant described the situation as follows:

“There are supposedly job descriptions, but if you ask me, they’re not very clear... There are a lot of gray areas.” (Participant 6).

Another participant similarly pointed out role ambiguity, stating, *“I’ve been given some responsibilities that shouldn’t be in my job description.” (Participant 9).*

4.7.4. Multitasking

Research findings indicate that human resources professionals often have to perform multiple functions simultaneously. Participants reported taking responsibility in various areas such as recruitment processes, payroll and personnel administration, training organization, operational processes, and regulatory compliance. This reveals that the human resources management position has a multifaceted and complex structure (Bakker & Demerouti, 2007). While multitasking is seen as an element that increases workload, it can also offer employees opportunities to gain experience in different areas and develop their professional skills. Therefore, this creates a dual effect in terms of both role diversity and professional learning (Hackman & Oldham, 1976).

One participant described the situation with the following words:

“This job has a legal side, an operational side, and a consulting side... It’s not something one person can do alone.” (Participant 4).

Similarly, another participant described the diversity of tasks as follows:

“Actually, I’m running two different departments... So I feel like I’m doing a job for two.” (Participant 5).

Overall, the findings regarding the nature of the job and the fit of skills indicate that human resources professionals perceive a significant alignment between their job and individual competencies. However, factors such as role ambiguity and multitasking can, in some cases, increase workload and limit the quality of working life. Therefore, job-person fit is considered a multidimensional element that should be addressed not only in terms of the alignment of individual competencies with job requirements, but also in conjunction with clarity of job descriptions and definite role boundaries.

4.8. Theme 6: Wage Policy and Economic Satisfaction

4.8.1. Fringe Benefits

Research findings indicate that fringe benefits are a significant element supporting employees' perception of economic satisfaction. Participants stated that meal and transportation support, private health insurance, individual retirement contributions, and various social support provided in addition to salary are generally sufficient. These practices are considered an important security and support mechanism for employees, especially considering the economic conditions in

Turkey. However, some participants indicated that the current fringe benefits remain at a basic level and that more comprehensive social support could be developed. It was also stated that position differences may affect the perceived benefit level of fringe benefits. This situation shows that while fringe benefits contribute to employee satisfaction, the level of satisfaction can vary depending on variables such as individual expectations and organizational position (Milkovich et al., 2014; Armstrong, 2012).

One participant described the situation as follows:

“Social amenities are adequate by Turkish standards... There is support such as food, transportation assistance and private health insurance.” (Participant 4).

Another participant expressed the need for improvement in fringe benefits with the following words:

“The benefits are there, but I think they need to be improved” (Participant 3).

4.8.2. Salary Satisfaction

The research findings indicate that a significant portion of participants are generally satisfied with their current salary levels. Participants stated that salaries are determined by considering criteria such as performance, responsibility, and contribution to the company. Performance-oriented salary policies, in particular, are emphasized as a factor that encourages employees to take initiative and contribute to the organization. However, some participants stated that they sometimes perceive a discrepancy between their individual performance and the salary they receive. This shows that salary satisfaction is influenced not only by organizational policies but also by individual expectations (Heneman & Judge, 2000; Gerhart & Rynes, 2003).

One participant expressed this situation as follows: *“I am satisfied with my salary and I think I got a good deal considering the working conditions.” (Participant 12).*

Another participant explained the performance-based compensation system with the following words:

“Salary increases are made taking into account the individual’s contribution to the company and performance.” (Participant 2).

4.8.3. Criteria-Based Compensation

The findings indicate that compensation processes in some organizations are conducted according to specific criteria. Participants stated that factors such as employees' education level, professional experience, foreign language proficiency, and performance results are taken into consideration in the wage determination process. In addition, maintaining internal wage balances and taking sector averages

into account also play an important role in determining wage policies (Milkovich et al., 2014).

It was noted that some institutions utilize 360-degree performance appraisal systems and various competency measurement tools, and that these practices contribute to the creation of a more transparent and systematic compensation structure. Participants also stated that in recent years, some institutions have made their compensation policies more structured and implemented regulations aimed at reducing wage inequalities (Gerhart & Rynes, 2003).

One participant described the process as follows:

“The salary is determined by taking into account the candidate’s experience, education, and salary levels within the sector.” (Participant 3).

Another participant explained the new regulations regarding wage policies as follows:

“In recent years, a compensation and benefits department has been established, and efforts have been made to make salaries fairer.” (Participant 6).

4.8.4. Inflationary Pressure

Participant assessments indicate that macroeconomic conditions, and particularly inflation, have a significant impact on employees' perceptions of economic satisfaction. Even though participants were partially satisfied with their current wages, they stated that high inflation rates reduced purchasing power and that wage increases could quickly become insufficient (Judge et al., 2010).

Some participants indicated that wage satisfaction is not solely dependent on organizational policies, but that factors such as developing individual skills and taking advantage of more competitive job opportunities also influence economic satisfaction. However, it is observed that rapidly increasing inflation negatively affects wage perception, and employees believe that their income may fall behind the market average in the long term (Card et al., 2012).

One participant described the situation with the following words:

“The wage increases we receive can fall below inflation, and after a while, wages can lag behind the market” (Participant 14).

4.8.5. Lack of Criteria in Wage

The research findings indicate a strong perception that salary determination processes in some organizations are not sufficiently systematic and transparent. Participants stated that salaries are often determined based on job title, and that factors such as the level of responsibility, risk factor, or added value provided to the company are not always adequately considered (Colquitt et al., 2001). This situation can lead to similar salaries being applied to employees with the same title despite varying levels of responsibility, weakening the perception of fairness among employees. Furthermore, some participants noted that applying salary increases at

the same rates to all employees does not adequately reflect performance differences (Adams, 1965).

One participant expressed the situation with the following words:

“Although there are differences in responsibilities among people working in the same position, salaries are often similar.” (Participant 4).

Another participant expressed their criticism of the wage policy as follows:

“I don't think it's a fair wage system... There can be significant salary differences” (Participant 5).

Overall, the findings regarding wage policy and economic satisfaction indicate that fringe benefits and performance-based wage practices support employees' economic satisfaction. However, inflationary pressures make it difficult to sustain wage increases and can negatively impact employees' purchasing power. Furthermore, the lack of sufficiently systematic and transparent wage-setting processes in some organizations can weaken the perception of organizational justice. Therefore, economic satisfaction should be evaluated not only in terms of wage level but also in conjunction with the transparency of wage policies, their alignment with performance, and the impact of macroeconomic conditions.

The code-matrix scanner shows how the themes identified in the research are distributed among the participants and which topics are repeated more frequently in the dataset. Figure 2 shows the code-matrix scanner created for the research. When the matrix is examined, it is seen that codes such as the presence of job security, work-life balance (positive), and salary satisfaction are mentioned by a significant portion of the participants. This indicates that factors such as trust, work order, and economic satisfaction play a decisive role when human resources professionals evaluate the quality of working life. However, the fact that codes such as work-life balance (negative), long working hours, and role ambiguity are also expressed by different participants reveals that the quality of working life is not only composed of positive experiences, but that some organizational and structural problems can also affect employee experience. The matrix also shows that themes such as organizational climate, career management, and the nature of the job are distributed with different intensities among the participants; it reveals that factors such as valuing ideas, open communication channels, and job-person fit are among the factors supporting the quality of working life.

Figure 2: Code-Matrix Browser

Source: Created by the authors via MAXQDA.

5. Conclusion and Discussion

This research aimed to examine human resources professionals' perceptions of their quality of work life within a qualitative research approach, and to reveal the fundamental organizational dynamics that shape this perception. The results showed that the quality of work life perceived by human resources professionals is not a one-dimensional construct; rather, it is shaped by a combination of numerous interconnected factors such as legal security, work-life balance, career management, organizational climate, the nature of the job, and wage policies. The findings indicate that when evaluating their quality of work life, human resources professionals consider not only economic benefits but also feelings of security, organizational predictability, managerial approach, clarity of job structure, and development opportunities as determining factors.

One of the key findings of the study is that legal security and the organizational structure generate a strong sense of trust among employees. Participants considered compliance with labor law, the existence of written procedures, transparent processes, and the protection of employee rights at the corporate level as fundamental components of quality of working life. This indicates that, for human resources professionals, quality of working life is shaped not only by individual experiences but also by the normative and institutional functioning of the organization. In particular, a high perception of job security suggests that employees have a more positive experience not only in terms of retaining their jobs but also in terms of psychological security and organizational belonging.

Another important finding of the research is that the work schedule and work-life balance dimensions exhibit a dual appearance. The findings show that hybrid and flexible work models can support work-life balance by providing time and spatial flexibility to human resources professionals. However, the same findings also reveal that this flexibility does not always produce positive results; when appropriate boundaries are not set, it can lead to the transfer of work into private life, an increased expectation of constant accessibility, and consequently, a disruption of work-life balance. In this respect, hybrid work appears not as a model that automatically produces employee well-being, but as a practice that gains meaning in conjunction with managerial boundaries, workload balance, and organizational culture.

Findings in the areas of career management and fairness indicate that merit- and criteria-based promotion systems are motivating for employees in organizations, but uncertainties and subjective interference in implementation can weaken this positive perception. While some participants positively evaluated systems based on education, experience, and performance, others stated that managerial initiative was too decisive in promotion processes, development opportunities were limited, and there was a lack of organizational support. This situation reveals that the perception of fairness in the quality of working life of human resources professionals is closely related not only to salary but also to the transparency and accessibility of career opportunities.

In terms of organizational climate and participation, open communication channels, accessibility to management, and the ability to express ideas have been found to be important elements supporting the quality of working life. However, it is understood that employee opinions are not always reflected in decision-making processes to the same extent, social activities remain limited, and structural problems that weaken social integration exist in some institutions. This finding shows that a healthy organizational climate is possible not only through open communication but also through employee participation producing effective results and strengthening social bonds.

In terms of job nature and qualification fit, most participants stated that they felt a strong fit between their work and their competencies. Skills such as interpersonal relationships, communication, empathy, analytical thinking, and legal

knowledge aligning with the human resources profession stand out as factors that strengthen job satisfaction and a sense of professional meaning. However, despite this positive picture, it is also observed that elements such as role ambiguity and multitasking can increase workload in some cases and negatively affect the quality of working life. This result shows that job-person fit alone is not sufficient; it needs to be supported by clear job descriptions and a balanced distribution of workload.

The findings regarding wage policy and economic satisfaction indicate a more heterogeneous structure. While some participants stated that they were satisfied with their wages and benefits, others expressed that there was insufficient transparency in the wage setting processes and that wage increases were not always commensurate with performance and responsibility levels. Furthermore, inflationary pressure emerged as a structural factor directly affecting wage satisfaction. This shows that economic satisfaction is related not only to the nominal wage level but also to whether wage policy is fair, predictable, and sustainable.

When the discussion aspect of the research is evaluated, it can be said that the findings are largely consistent with the literature on the multidimensional nature of quality of working life. Dimensions such as fair wages, safe working conditions, development opportunities, job security, and organizational participation, emphasized in Walton's framework of quality of working life, were also found to be decisive in the experiences of human resources professionals in this research. However, the unique contribution of this study is that it considers human resources professionals not only as actors implementing organizational policies but also as a group of employees who directly experience the effects of these policies. In this respect, the research reveals that the perceptions of human resources employees regarding their own quality of working life offer important clues about the organizations' understanding of human resources management.

In conclusion, improving the quality of working life for human resources professionals cannot be achieved solely through increased wage levels. Organizations need to develop holistic human resources policies that strengthen legal protection, support work-life balance, ensure transparency in career processes, encourage open communication, and reduce role ambiguity. Specifically, clarifying the boundaries of hybrid work arrangements, systematizing development and promotion processes, increasing corporate practices that support social integration, and strengthening transparency in compensation policies will be effective in improving the quality of working life.

From a future research perspective, a comparative examination of the quality of working life of human resources professionals in different cities, sectors, and organizational scales could make significant contributions to the literature. Furthermore, mixed-methods research designs, supported by quantitative methods, could allow for testing the themes presented in this study on larger samples. In addition, it is recommended that the effects of variables such as hybrid work, emotional labor, role conflict, organizational justice, and burnout on the quality of working life of human resources professionals be investigated in greater depth. In

particular, the specific experiences arising from human resources professionals simultaneously holding both organizational practitioner and employee identities should be addressed in more detail in future studies.

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